

Generalization of the Newtonian gravitation.

Juan Luis PELAYO MADARIAGA*

July 20, 2024

ABSTRACT

From the Newton's Laws and with the kinematics of orbital motion, a series of equations can be established to better understand the movement between two massive masses.

Contents

1	Convention of the Einstein sum.	2
2	Introduction.	2
3	Metric of the base.	3
3.1	Base vectors and metric tensor.	4
4	Trajectory and orbit.	5
5	Gravitational field.	8
5.1	Energy and energy dependence.	9
6	Accelerations.	10
6.1	Orbital tangential acceleration.	10
6.2	Normal orbital acceleration.	11
7	References.	12

1 Convention of the Einstein sum.

Whenever in this document there are Latin or Greek indices facing each other, it means that there is an implicit summation under the possible values of these. The Greek indices will take values (1,2,3), and the Latin indices will take values (1,2).

2 Introduction.

In this paper we will be describing the equations of gravitation of Newton, from the postulates of Kepler. We will try to generalize all the equations in the most simplified way possible within a non-relativistic spatial framework. In this paper I want to introduce a mathematical tool that will help us locate bodies in space, in case this tends to change. I have decided to call it a ‘rotational transform of a vector’. It is simply a vector that will depend on two parameters θ and ϕ . These parameters will vary to rotate the vector in two directions: θ will rotate the vector next to the plane xy with the axis x as the axis of rotation. ϕ will rotate the vector next to the plane xy with the axis y as the rotation axis. It should be clarified that the same vector can be rotated in both directions at different angles without the vector being affected in its module.

Let’s start by defining these vectors. For this we will begin with a classic vector:

$$v^\mu = \begin{bmatrix} v^1 \\ v^2 \\ v^3 \end{bmatrix} \quad (1)$$

The rotation matrices shall be:

$$R_x(\theta) = \begin{bmatrix} 1 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & \cos \theta & -\sin \theta \\ 0 & \sin \theta & \cos \theta \end{bmatrix} \quad R_y(\phi) = \begin{bmatrix} \cos \phi & 0 & \sin \phi \\ 0 & 1 & 0 \\ -\sin \phi & 0 & \cos \phi \end{bmatrix} \quad (2)$$

When making the following product of matrices, we obtain:

$$R_x(\theta)v^\mu = \begin{bmatrix} 1 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & \cos \theta & -\sin \theta \\ 0 & \sin \theta & \cos \theta \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} v^1 \\ v^2 \\ v^3 \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} v^1 \\ v^2 \cos \theta - v^3 \sin \theta \\ v^2 \sin \theta + v^3 \cos \theta \end{bmatrix} = v^{\mu'} \quad (3)$$

If we now make the matrix product:

$$\begin{aligned}
R_y(\phi)v^{\mu'} &= \begin{bmatrix} \cos \phi & 0 & \sin \phi \\ 0 & 1 & 0 \\ -\sin \phi & 0 & \cos \phi \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} v^1 \\ v^2 \cos \theta - v^3 \sin \theta \\ v^2 \sin \theta + v^3 \cos \theta \end{bmatrix} \\
&= \begin{bmatrix} v^1 \cos \phi + v^2 \sin \phi \sin \theta + v^3 \sin \phi \cos \theta \\ v^2 \cos \theta - v^3 \sin \theta \\ -v^1 \sin \phi + v^2 \cos \phi \sin \theta + v^3 \cos \phi \cos \theta \end{bmatrix} \tag{4}
\end{aligned}$$

To the result of the matrix product, we will call it as its initial vector, but with a bar above or with a $\mathcal{R}$ with vector in brackets to know that the a transformable vector:

$$\mathcal{R}[v^\mu] = \bar{v}^\mu = \begin{bmatrix} v^1 \cos \phi + v^2 \sin \phi \sin \theta + v^3 \sin \phi \cos \theta \\ v^2 \cos \theta - v^3 \sin \theta \\ -v^1 \sin \phi + v^2 \cos \phi \sin \theta + v^3 \cos \phi \cos \theta \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} \bar{v}^1 \\ \bar{v}^2 \\ \bar{v}^3 \end{bmatrix} \tag{5}$$

3 Metric of the base.

We will start from the smallest position vector defined in a space. We will represent it with differentials:

$$ds^\mu = \begin{bmatrix} ds^1 \\ ds^2 \\ ds^3 \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} dx \\ dy \\ dz \end{bmatrix} \tag{6}$$

We will calculate the module of this vector, all raised to the square. This will be represented as ds^2 , this being the minimum measure in space:

$$ds^2 = dx^2 + dy^2 + dz^2 \tag{7}$$

The above expression is the metric of a $\mathbb{R}^3$ Euclidean space. Now we take the rotational transform of the vector ds^μ , and we get:

$$d\bar{s}^\mu = \begin{bmatrix} dx \cos \phi + dy \sin \phi \sin \theta + dz \sin \phi \cos \theta \\ dy \cos \theta - dz \sin \theta \\ -dx \sin \phi + dy \cos \phi \sin \theta + dz \cos \phi \cos \theta \end{bmatrix} \tag{8}$$

We will calculate the module of $d\bar{s}^\mu$. We will call it $d\bar{s}^2$:

$$d\bar{s}^2 = [dx \cos \phi + dy \sin \phi \sin \theta + dz \sin \phi \cos \theta]^2 \quad (9)$$

$$+ [dy \cos \theta - dz \sin \theta]^2 \quad (10)$$

$$+ [-dx \sin \phi + dy \cos \phi \sin \theta + dz \cos \phi \cos \theta]^2 \quad (11)$$

If we develop it, it is:

$$d\bar{s}^2 = dx^2 + dy^2 + dz^2 \quad (12)$$

Thus:

$$ds^2 = d\bar{s}^2 = dx^2 + dy^2 + dz^2 \quad (13)$$

We have just shown that it does not matter that we transform a metric or a vector, because it will always remain constant in module.

3.1 Base vectors and metric tensor.

The vectors of a three-dimensional Euclidean space are:

$$\vec{r}_1 = \begin{bmatrix} 1 \\ 0 \\ 0 \end{bmatrix} \quad \vec{r}_2 = \begin{bmatrix} 0 \\ 1 \\ 0 \end{bmatrix} \quad \vec{r}_3 = \begin{bmatrix} 0 \\ 0 \\ 1 \end{bmatrix} \quad (14)$$

If we take the rotational transform of each vector, we have:

$$\mathcal{R}[\vec{r}_1] = \begin{bmatrix} \cos \phi \\ 0 \\ -\sin \phi \end{bmatrix} \quad \mathcal{R}[\vec{r}_2] = \begin{bmatrix} \sin \phi \sin \theta \\ \cos \theta \\ \cos \phi \sin \theta \end{bmatrix} \quad \mathcal{R}[\vec{r}_3] = \begin{bmatrix} \sin \phi \cos \theta \\ -\sin \theta \\ \cos \phi \cos \theta \end{bmatrix} \quad (15)$$

We define the metric tensor as the matrix that collects all combinations of scalar products of two vectors of the base.

$$p_{\mu\nu} = \vec{r}_\mu \otimes \vec{r}_\nu \quad (16)$$

Let us remember that the scalar product is not altered by rotational transformations, so it does not matter if we express the tensor product of the base vectors, or of the rotational transformations of the base vectors, or as the rotational transformation of the metric tensor:

$$p_{\mu\nu} = \bar{p}_{\mu\nu} = \vec{r}_\mu \otimes \vec{r}_\nu = \mathcal{R}[\vec{r}_\mu] \otimes \mathcal{R}[\vec{r}_\nu] \quad (17)$$

The metric matrix the metric tensor, is defined as:

$$p_{\mu\nu} = \bar{p}_{\mu\nu} = \vec{r}_\mu \otimes \vec{r}_\nu = \mathcal{R}[\vec{r}_\mu] \otimes \mathcal{R}[\vec{r}_\nu] = \begin{bmatrix} \vec{r}_1 \cdot \vec{r}_1 & \vec{r}_1 \cdot \vec{r}_2 & \vec{r}_1 \cdot \vec{r}_3 \\ \vec{r}_2 \cdot \vec{r}_1 & \vec{r}_2 \cdot \vec{r}_2 & \vec{r}_2 \cdot \vec{r}_3 \\ \vec{r}_3 \cdot \vec{r}_1 & \vec{r}_3 \cdot \vec{r}_2 & \vec{r}_3 \cdot \vec{r}_3 \end{bmatrix} \quad (18)$$

Let us recall that:

$$\vec{r}_1 \cdot \vec{r}_1 = \vec{r}_2 \cdot \vec{r}_2 = \vec{r}_3 \cdot \vec{r}_3 = 1 \quad (19)$$

Let us remember that:

$$\vec{r}_1 \cdot \vec{r}_2 = \vec{r}_2 \cdot \vec{r}_1 = \vec{r}_1 \cdot \vec{r}_3 = \vec{r}_3 \cdot \vec{r}_1 = \vec{r}_2 \cdot \vec{r}_3 = \vec{r}_3 \cdot \vec{r}_2 = 0 \quad (20)$$

If we replace these results in the metric tensor, we have:

$$p_{\mu\nu} = \begin{bmatrix} 1 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 1 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 1 \end{bmatrix} \quad (21)$$

If we look closely, this matrix results in a Kronecker delta, or an identity matrix:

$$p_{\mu\nu} = \begin{bmatrix} 1 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 1 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 1 \end{bmatrix} = \delta_{\mu\nu} \quad (22)$$

From now on we will call the metric tensor $p_{\mu\nu}$ to know that it remains the same after taking its rotational transform.

Having said that, we can express the metric as:

$$dx^2 + dy^2 + dz^2 = p_{\mu\nu} d\sigma^\mu d\sigma^\nu \quad (23)$$

4 Trajectory and orbit.

Let's define a function $S(t)$ that will describe the orbit of the minor body. The angle that sweeps the planet over a period of time is equal to the angular velocity multiplied by the time, so the equation is:

$$S(t) = \begin{cases} x(t) = \rho \cos(\omega t) \\ y(t) = r \sin(\omega t) \\ z(t) = 0 \end{cases} \quad (24)$$

The magnitudes seen in the equation above are: ρ is the length of the major half-axis of the orbit, r is the length of the minor half-axis of the orbit, ω is the angular velocity and t is the time. We will define a new magnitude, which will be the distance between the focus of the orbit and its center, since the central body (which is orbited) is located in one of the foci of the orbit. This parameter is called focal length, and is defined by the letter γ :

$$\gamma = \sqrt{\rho^2 - r^2} \quad (25)$$

Figure 1: System

In the previous image we can see these magnitudes more visually. We will describe the equation of the orbit in matrix form:

$$S(t) = \begin{bmatrix} \rho \cos(\omega t) \\ r \sin(\omega t) \\ 0 \end{bmatrix} \quad (26)$$

We will take the rotational transform of $S(t)$

$$\mathcal{R}[S(t)] = \bar{S}(t) = \begin{bmatrix} \rho \cos \phi \cos(\omega t) + r \sin \phi \sin \theta \sin(\omega t) \\ r \cos \theta \sin(\omega t) \\ -\rho \sin \phi \cos(\omega t) + r \cos \phi \sin \theta \sin(\omega t) \end{bmatrix} \quad (27)$$

We will add an initial offset ψ_0 to the arguments of the trigonometric functions containing the variable t :

$$\bar{S}(t) = \begin{bmatrix} \rho \cos \phi \cos(\omega t + \psi_0) + r \sin \phi \sin \theta \sin(\omega t + \psi_0) \\ r \cos \theta \sin(\omega t + \psi_0) \\ -\rho \sin \phi \cos(\omega t + \psi_0) + r \cos \phi \sin \theta \sin(\omega t + \psi_0) \end{bmatrix} \quad (28)$$

Having said this, we will define the transformable vector of orbital position of the minor body:

$$\bar{\sigma}^\mu = \begin{bmatrix} \rho \cos \phi \cos(\omega t + \psi_0) + r \sin \phi \sin \theta \sin(\omega t + \psi_0) \\ r \cos \theta \sin(\omega t + \psi_0) \\ -\rho \sin \phi \cos(\omega t + \psi_0) + r \cos \phi \sin \theta \sin(\omega t + \psi_0) \end{bmatrix} \quad (29)$$

Its full expression is:

$$\bar{\sigma}^\mu \vec{r}_\mu^\rightarrow = [\rho \cos \phi \cos(\omega t + \psi_0) + r \sin \phi \sin \theta \sin(\omega t + \psi_0)] \vec{r}_1^\rightarrow \quad (30)$$

$$+ [r \cos \theta \sin(\omega t + \psi_0)] \vec{r}_2^\rightarrow \quad (31)$$

$$+ [-\rho \sin \phi \cos(\omega t + \psi_0) + r \cos \phi \sin \theta \sin(\omega t + \psi_0)] \vec{r}_3^\rightarrow \quad (32)$$

Next, we define the transformable orbital velocity vector as:

$$\bar{v}^\mu = \frac{d\bar{\sigma}^\mu}{dt} = \begin{bmatrix} -\rho\omega \cos \phi \sin(\omega t + \psi_0) + r\omega \sin \phi \sin \theta \cos(\omega t + \psi_0) \\ r\omega \cos \theta \cos(\omega t + \psi_0) \\ \rho\omega \sin \phi \sin(\omega t + \psi_0) + r\omega \cos \phi \sin \theta \cos(\omega t + \psi_0) \end{bmatrix} \quad (33)$$

Its full expression is:

$$\bar{v}^\mu \vec{r}_\mu^\rightarrow = \frac{d\bar{\sigma}^\mu}{dt} \vec{r}_\mu^\rightarrow = [-\rho\omega \cos \phi \sin(\omega t + \psi_0) + r\omega \sin \phi \sin \theta \cos(\omega t + \psi_0)] \vec{r}_1^\rightarrow \quad (34)$$

$$+ [r\omega \cos \theta \cos(\omega t + \psi_0)] \vec{r}_2^\rightarrow \quad (35)$$

$$+ [\rho\omega \sin \phi \sin(\omega t + \psi_0) + r\omega \cos \phi \sin \theta \cos(\omega t + \psi_0)] \vec{r}_3^\rightarrow \quad (36)$$

We will now define the transformable vector of orbital acceleration as:

$$\bar{a}^\mu = \frac{d\bar{v}^\mu}{dt} = \begin{bmatrix} -\rho\omega^2 \cos \phi \cos(\omega t + \psi_0) - r\omega^2 \sin \phi \sin \theta \sin(\omega t + \psi_0) \\ -r\omega^2 \cos \theta \sin(\omega t + \psi_0) \\ \rho\omega^2 \sin \phi \cos(\omega t + \psi_0) - r\omega^2 \cos \phi \sin \theta \sin(\omega t + \psi_0) \end{bmatrix} \quad (37)$$

Its full expression is:

$$\bar{a}^\mu \bar{r}_\mu^\rightarrow = \frac{d\bar{v}^\mu}{dt} \bar{r}_\mu^\rightarrow = [-\rho\omega^2 \cos\phi \cos(\omega t + \psi_0) - r\omega^2 \sin\phi \sin\theta \sin(\omega t + \psi_0)] \bar{r}_1^\rightarrow \quad (38)$$

$$+ [-r\omega^2 \cos\theta \sin(\omega t + \psi_0)] \bar{r}_2^\rightarrow \quad (39)$$

$$+ [\rho\omega^2 \sin\phi \cos(\omega t + \psi_0) - r\omega^2 \cos\phi \sin\theta \sin(\omega t + \psi_0)] \bar{r}_3^\rightarrow \quad (40)$$

5 Gravitational field.

The definition of gravitational force is $F = G \frac{mM}{r^2}$, being m the mass of the body orbiting, M the mass of the central body, r the distance between both and G , the Gravitational constant. The distance between the two bodies varies with the elliptical orbit. Let's deduce a function that gives us the value of distance for any instant of t . We only care about the function module, so we will not work on its rotational transformations. Let's start by defining an elliptic orbit of radius ρ and r , like the three-dimensional one, but this time in $\mathbb{R}^2$. Let γ be the distance between the central body and the center of the orbit.

$$\gamma = \sqrt{\rho^2 - r^2} \quad (41)$$

Let R be the point of the orbit where the orbiting body is located. It is defined by:

$$R = (\rho \cos(\omega t + \psi_0), r \sin(\omega t + \psi_0)) \quad (42)$$

We define the Φ point where the central body is located:

$$\Phi = (-\gamma, 0) \quad (43)$$

Now we calculate the vector that has origin in Φ , and destination in R , we calculate its module and have the exact distance between both bodies. This vector shall be called h^i :

$$h^i = \overrightarrow{\Phi R} = R - \Phi = \begin{bmatrix} \rho \cos(\omega t + \psi_0) + \gamma \\ r \sin(\omega t + \psi_0) \end{bmatrix} \quad (44)$$

Its square modulus will be expressed as $h^i h^j \delta_{ij}$, with δ_{ij} being the metric tensor of a two-dimensional Euclidean space. In this case, it matches the identity matrix $\delta_{ij} = \begin{bmatrix} 1 & 0 \\ 0 & 1 \end{bmatrix}$.

All this said, the module of the h^i vector is:

$$(h^i h^j \delta_{ij})^{1/2} = \sqrt{(\rho \cos(\omega t + \psi_0) + \gamma)^2 + r^2 \sin^2(\omega t + \psi_0)} \quad (45)$$

From now on we will call this function as radial distance, or with the letter h to simplify it, so:

$$h = \sqrt{(\rho \cos(\omega t + \psi_0) + \gamma)^2 + r^2 \sin^2(\omega t + \psi_0)} \quad (46)$$

So, the gravitational force is:

$$F_g = G \frac{mM}{h^2} \quad (47)$$

Since the orbit is stable, that is, it does not deform, there must be a centrifugal force equal to the gravitational force to compensate for it. Let's define this force:

$$F_c = ma_n = \frac{mv^2}{r} \quad (48)$$

Recalling that the radius, now is a variable radius we have named as h , and the speed module is $\bar{v}^\mu \bar{r}_\mu^\rightarrow \bar{v}^\nu \bar{r}_\nu^\rightarrow = \bar{v}^\mu \bar{v}^\nu p_{\mu\nu}$, so:

$$F_c = \frac{m\bar{v}^\mu \bar{v}^\nu}{h} p_{\mu\nu} \quad (49)$$

As we said before, $F_g = F_c$:

$$\frac{m\bar{v}^\mu \bar{v}^\nu}{h} p_{\mu\nu} = G \frac{mM}{h^2} \quad (50)$$

If we simplify:

$$\bar{v}^\mu \bar{v}^\nu p_{\mu\nu} = \frac{GM}{h} \quad (51)$$

If we calculate the module of the orbital velocity squared by definition, it is:

$$\bar{v}^\mu \bar{v}^\nu p_{\mu\nu} = v^\mu v^\nu p_{\mu\nu} = \rho^2 \omega^2 \sin^2(\omega t + \psi_0) + r^2 \omega^2 \cos^2(\omega t + \psi_0) \quad (52)$$

5.1 Energy and energy dependence.

We define the energy dependence with the letter Q , and this will be equal to the orbital velocity module squared:

$$Q = v^\mu v^\nu p_{\mu\nu} = \rho^2 \omega^2 \sin^2(\omega t + \psi_0) + r^2 \omega^2 \cos^2(\omega t + \psi_0) \quad (53)$$

Let us note that the orbital velocity squared is also (51), so:

$$Q = \frac{GM}{h} \quad (54)$$

We have two different definitions for the same magnitude.

The energy of a body in orbit is defined by the sum of its kinetic energy and its gravitational potential energy, thus:

$$E = E_c + E_g = \frac{1}{2}mv^\mu v^\nu p_{\mu\nu} - G\frac{mM}{h} \quad (55)$$

If we look at the summations of the equation above, $v^\mu v^\nu p_{\mu\nu}$ can be substituted by the energy dependency, and $\frac{GM}{h}$ (in the second member) can also be substituted. Then it remains:

$$E = \frac{1}{2}mQ - mQ = -\frac{1}{2}mQ \quad (56)$$

As we can see, the total energy can be summed up in a single equation, simplifying the results.

6 Accelerations.

6.1 Orbital tangential acceleration.

The orbital tangential acceleration modulus is defined as the time derivative of the orbital velocity module.

$$(a_t^\mu a_t^\nu p_{\mu\nu})^{1/2} = \frac{d(v^\mu v^\nu p_{\mu\nu})^{1/2}}{dt} \quad (57)$$

If we develop this, it is:

$$\frac{d(v^\mu v^\nu p_{\mu\nu})^{1/2}}{dt} = \frac{\rho^2 \omega^3 \sin(2\omega t + 2\psi_0) - r^2 \omega^3 \sin(2\omega t + 2\psi_0)}{2\sqrt{\rho^2 \omega^2 \sin^2(\omega t + \psi_0) + r^2 \omega^2 \cos^2(\omega t + \psi_0)}} \quad (58)$$

If we continue to develop it, we will find that:

$$\frac{d(v^\mu v^\nu p_{\mu\nu})^{1/2}}{dt} = \frac{\omega^2 \gamma^2 \sin(2\omega t + 2\psi_0)}{2\sqrt{\rho^2 \sin^2(\omega t + \psi_0) + r^2 \cos^2(\omega t + \psi_0)}} \quad (59)$$

Next we will define the unitary vector that will be responsible for giving direction and sense to the orbital tangential acceleration. We will call it tangential orbital unitary vector transformable designating with the letter τ .

$$\bar{\tau}^\mu \vec{r}_\mu = \frac{\bar{v}^\mu}{(v^\mu v^\nu p_{\mu\nu})^{1/2}} \vec{r}_\mu \quad (60)$$

The transformable orbital tangential acceleration vector is defined as the product of its módulo by the unitized transformable orbital tangential vector:

$$\bar{a}_t^\mu \vec{r}_\mu^\rightarrow = \frac{(a_t^\mu a_t^\nu p_{\mu\nu})^{1/2} \bar{v}^\mu}{(v^\mu v^\nu p_{\mu\nu})^{1/2}} \vec{r}_\mu^\rightarrow \quad (61)$$

6.2 Normal orbital acceleration.

The module of orbital normal acceleration can be defined as:

$$(a_n^\mu a_n^\nu p_{\mu\nu})^{1/2} = \frac{v^\mu v^\nu}{h} p_{\mu\nu} \quad (62)$$

Next we will define the normal orbital transformable unit vector:

$$\bar{n}^\mu \vec{r}_\mu^\rightarrow = \frac{\frac{d\bar{\tau}^\mu \vec{r}_\mu^\rightarrow}{dt}}{\left| \frac{d(\bar{\tau}^\mu \bar{\tau}^\nu p_{\mu\nu})}{dt} \right|} \quad (63)$$

We will first calculate the denominator of the fraction:

$$\frac{d\bar{\tau}^\mu \vec{r}_\mu^\rightarrow}{dt} = \frac{d}{dt} \left(\frac{\bar{v}^\mu \vec{r}_\mu^\rightarrow}{\bar{v}^\mu \bar{v}^\nu p_{\mu\nu}} \right) \vec{r}_\mu^\rightarrow = \frac{\bar{a}^\mu (v^\mu v^\nu p_{\mu\nu})^{1/2} - \bar{v}^\mu (a_t^\mu a_t^\nu p_{\mu\nu})^{1/2}}{v^\mu v^\nu p_{\mu\nu}} \vec{r}_\mu^\rightarrow \quad (64)$$

To simplify the notation, we will call the previous vector $\bar{\beta}^\mu \vec{r}_\mu^\rightarrow$:

$$\frac{d\bar{\tau}^\mu \vec{r}_\mu^\rightarrow}{dt} = \bar{\beta}^\mu \vec{r}_\mu^\rightarrow = \frac{\bar{a}^\mu (v^\mu v^\nu p_{\mu\nu})^{1/2} - \bar{v}^\mu (a_t^\mu a_t^\nu p_{\mu\nu})^{1/2}}{v^\mu v^\nu p_{\mu\nu}} \vec{r}_\mu^\rightarrow \quad (65)$$

Having said this, let us go back to equation (63), and rewrite it:

$$\bar{n}^\mu \vec{r}_\mu^\rightarrow = \frac{\bar{\beta}^\mu \vec{r}_\mu^\rightarrow}{(\beta^\mu \beta^\nu p_{\mu\nu})^{1/2}} \quad (66)$$

The transformable vector of normal orbital acceleration remains:

$$\bar{a}_n^\mu \vec{r}_\mu^\rightarrow = \frac{v^\mu v^\nu \bar{\beta}^\mu p_{\mu\nu}}{h (\beta^\mu \beta^\nu p_{\mu\nu})^{1/2}} \vec{r}_\mu^\rightarrow \quad (67)$$

7 References.

- [1] Orbital velocity: <https://es.wikipedia.org/wiki/Velocidad-orbital>